

AUTOMATION OF WORK WITH E-MAIL AND ROBOTICS SYSTEM CONTROL SYSTEM

Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi

Student of Nukus Mining Institute:

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Abstract.

In this article, the workflow for controlling bots in a technological robotics system robotization is related to automation of processes, Artificial way intelligence used to obtain information, classification etc. are proposed. The bot is equipped with many is a software system with features that make working with e-mail a stress-free job. This automatic access to the mailbox through protected channels, separates, categorizes and places e-mail messages in different tabs, downloads attached files, creates different directories and stores downloaded files performs the distribution process to the appropriate directories. It contains unhelpful emails and is periodic clears garbage memory. It is also possible to train the bot to change its name and attached files with sender/applicant names For convenience, it is possible to develop a technological scheme of the job application filling system. A bot has been developed and tested using the UiPath tool to improve performance and a technological scheme of the system is drawn up. The document also discusses possible and features that can be added to the bot are included.

Keywords: Email automation system, artificial intelligence robot system, robotic process automation, technological scheme of expert systems, virtual in technical systems assistant, UiPath.

INTRODUCTION

Enterprise filing system technology is very important tedious task to solve job/internship application via e-mail. That is why, automation is very important in this service, that's why the working population of the world can be freed from excessive red tape and serves to prevent unnecessary workloads of managing their mailboxes. With that we we proposed an approach to create an email assistant and adept at handling many of the tasks involved in organizing people's e-mail we have begun to work on other important aspects of the speed of utechnologies, we compared its performance indicators. This stops wasting time sorting and inbox, add, delete, etc. In addition to these problems in the problem category of finding similar substructures is an NP-complete problem in nature and needs opportunities to create an efficient algorithm for solving the problem of exponential order have been created. The first is the emergence of artificial intelligence changed the business management process associated with the period and the use of machines instead of humans, hence the use of robots process automation. This is not only a paradigm shift supports organizations, but increases income by reducing. Similarly, registering new customers requires several documents. A lot of time is spent on investigations and information. This whole process can be changed and to a number of tasks related to training a robot system and replicated through the relevant systems. Well, now that's all the process can be perfected and controlled by robots 24/7 there are options to

avoid any mistakes. This technology is different from others and sectors, frequent repetition of the process can be avoided. Also the operation is intensive, it is not necessary to hire employees here the initiative is subjective to the already established rule and creating a technological scheme of standards will facilitate this work process. The proposed bot is UiPath, developed with the help of a robot, a technological is a process automation tool. Equipped with this it is based on the following features to make email handling a stress-free affair. This automatically access the mailbox through secure channels and separates useful and non-useful emails based on the system performs its activity according to the provided keywords. It classifies letters differently and directories, e.g. Job (for job related emails, CVs, resumes) and receipts (for bills and invoices). Will download creates attachments from classified emails different catalogs for different categories and stores them as well copies the downloaded files to the respective directories. This technological system drives and junk mails in the trash. The proposed Email Client Automation is a robotic system framework with autonomous capabilities for efficient email enhanced functionality for smart categorization of communications and incoming emails list of recommendations. The user can write in the reply that can be sent to each customer (customer email selected by their identifiers) belongs to the category defined by the user personally. This process still allows the user and has full control over the task. In addition, this approach reduces the time and energy required to generate a response and email from scratch and also saves you the trouble of trawling through your entire inbox to find similar emails. It belongs to the user defined category. The categorization scheme is defined by the user and can have K categories. For example, for online in the case of a shopping application, an organization can receive an email with the specification details of its product or complaints, shareholders or their working relationships can be considered. All these letters can be divided into different types and the system places folders such as customer complaints, business transactions, inquiries, finance, etc.

Picture 1. Scheme and stages of the automation system of the program

Email Assistant is a robotic process attached to the system

The email assistant will have the following features functions and features differ from each other.

- # Protected bot that can login when allowed to do and is done with system permission.
- # Identified senders without manual inspection devices are sorted.
- # Save user time by not opening emails there are opportunities for technological cooperation with advertising agencies/companies.
- # Increase user comfort by classifying the automation system and attach mail IDs to different categories.
- # Automatically download add-ons if available and reduce paperwork without human intervention.
- # Sort the downloaded attachments into two folders.
- Useful and not useful.

Classify them again in a useful folder and various folders - accounts, resume, offer letter, create a separate item for invoices and more. Some of the parameters by which the effectiveness of an email client automation bot is measured are:

- * Efficiency is the ratio of useful work done by the system.
- * Time consumption is the unit of time taken by the system for processing and transfer.
- * Accuracy - This shows the exact state of the system.

To study the effectiveness of the system, a Gmail account was used, in which incoming e-mail messages are read and answered using two cases

CASE1: Processing e-mail without implementing a robot (ie manually).

CASE2: Email processing with robot implementation (i.e. automation).

Actions such as opening e-mail using user credentials, checking received mail, selecting important letters, reading mail content and replying to letters individually is done manually. Case 1, while in Case 2, the robot does it without any human intervention for the user.

Results and discussions

The proposed Email Client Automation is a robotic system with autonomous capabilities for effective email. enhanced functionality for smart categorization of communications and incoming emails a list of recommendations is formed. The user can write in the reply that can be sent to each customer (customer email ids) are personally in the same category. This approach is still a background process that enables and the user has full control over the task. It also reduces the time and energy required to create perform the same task from scratch or sift through the entire inbox to find similar requests. The following advances can be made to make your email client automation robot more efficient soon and use the email communication channel. Intelligent email separation and routing system capabilities used to use email management functions such as summarization, traffic management, business process discoveries etc. The system may also include categorizing e-mail messages by subject discussion on optimizing email routing and distribution. Can be combined to create artificial intelligence is accepted as a subject-based answer.

CONCLUSION

This article is about email automation and shows the control system diagram. Automation eliminates paperwork and typing automatically entered into the mailbox management system. In this regard, he It offers a simple and innovative workflow for designing intelligent Email Assistant with UiPath is a Robotization Technology System tool. Robot provides a good level of comfort to its users with its equipment the level of functionality is very high. It automatically and securely logs in and classifies and sub-classifies emails based on mailbox, remembers important keywords. It will automatically download, attachments and stores them in different folders respectively classified emails. It can also rename attached files according to requirements. The bot does not cancel human commands/actions to face any problem security threat. Workflow has been implemented and tested done on a few test emails and found it works. According to the specified functions. Using Windows Activity, the bot can be trained to rename email attachments To the desired names if the application needs to do this the real world. For example, it can rename resumes <candidate_name>_<highest_qualified>_<app_date > etc. It can also send mail to the concerned candidates will be done through interview call. Otelbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute at the Navoi State University of Mining and Technologies, is conducting research on technology automation processes. Azizbek

is conducting research on robotics and automation technology of modern technological processes in mining enterprises. Azizbek's articles on technologies and technological processes in mining enterprises were published in international magazines. He is very interested in technological processes, currently studying computer systems management, applications used in mining enterprises. Azizbek is a 4th year student and has been following the processes in mining enterprises for a long time. He is interested in mining and loading processes, flotation and beneficiation processes, and the structure of metal melting furnaces in mining enterprises.

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